

MATERIALS FOR STUDY OF FOOD ADDITIVE TOXICOLOGY

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Abstract: Organoleptic, physicochemical, microbiological, technological properties, as well as quality and safety indicators are determined in the hygienic toxicological examination of food additives. The immunological activity of the "Mella croissan" feed additive was studied. Food mixture at a dose of 413 mg/kg did not have a negative effect on the amount of IgG and IgM class immunoglobulins in the peripheral blood serum of experimental animals.

Keywords: health, hygiene, toxicology, biologically active supplement, immunoglobulin, blood serum, food industry.

Nutrition is the most important factor affecting the human body, and proper and rational nutrition is a guarantee of health. Scientific and technical progress has created a demand for a new approach to the production of food products. This is often caused by errors and frauds in the process of artificially improving the taste of food and drinks and adding various spices to them in order to extend their shelf life, to make their appearance pleasing to the eye and increase appetite. As the chemical and food industries developed, countless by-products appeared that could be synthesized and used in place of spices. First, they allow to extend the shelf life of food and to deliver it to any corner of the Earth, and secondly, they give a beautiful appearance and a pleasant smell to soft drinks and arouse a pleasant appetite[1.5.9]. Experts say that in 2007, the development of nutritional supplements in the world increased by 30 billion dollars, and by 2010, it

increased by 20-25%. Every year, the production of food additives in European countries is increasing by 2%, in the USA by 4.4%, and in Asia by 10-15%. There are 1500 types of additives used in the food industry in the USA, more than 1200 in the European Union, and more than 400 types in Russia. is being used. Due to the fact that food additives used in the food industry in developed countries are increasing day by day, it is necessary to conduct various experiments and laboratory tests to reduce their unpleasant effects on the human body, therefore, toxicological evaluation and hygienic standardization of food additives is an urgent problem[6.8].

Biologically active additives are the etiological and pathogenetic factors that prevent diseases. A person's health depends 12% on the level of the health care system, 18% on genetic factors, and 70% on life activities, in particular on eating habits [5.6]. About five hundred different additives are used in the food industry, and the number of their combinations is several times more. How artificial ingredients, that is, food additives with integral components, affect the human body is one of the most interesting problems for consumers. In addition, there are now prestigious international organizations engaged in the study of this issue. For example, Joint Committee of Experts on Food Additives - (JECFA) controls their quality. Of course, according to the results of research, changes are being made to the list of food additives harmful to health. All food additives intended for use require hygienic toxicological tests. Organoleptic, physico-chemical, microbiological, technological characteristics as well as quality and safety indicators are determined in the hygienic toxicological examination of food additives. In Article 24, "Tests on food raw materials, food products, their production, transportation, storage and sale", import and production of new food additives, specially added biologically active substances into the Republic of Uzbekistan is restricted only to toxicology- it is specified that it is allowed only

after a hygienic assessment with the permission of the Chief State Sanitary Doctor of the Republic of Uzbekistan. [1.2.3.4.7].

" Mella croissan " nutritional supplement was made in Germany and is in the form of white powder. It contains high-quality wheat flour, nutritional gluten, sugar, salt, milk serum, milk powder, etc. The nutritional value of 100 g of the product is as follows: proteins - 23.1g, fats - 2.2g, carbohydrates - 54.5g, energy value 1419 kDj/335 kcal. Based on the above, the immunological activity of the nutritional supplement was studied. Determining the immunological activity of biologically active additives added to food products under In vivo conditions is important in evaluating the biological safety of food additives. The immunological activity of the food additive was studied in samples of peripheral blood serum of experimental animals, using the commercial kits of the Russian "Vector-Best" production company. The concentration of IgG and IgM class immunoglobulins was determined by solid-phase immunoenzymatic analysis and the following results were obtained. After feeding white rats with a dose of 413 mg/kg of the food mixture, samples were taken in the peripheral blood serum. The amount of IgG and IgM class immunoglobulins in the peripheral blood serum of the experimental animals (white rats) was shown in the table. When exposed to "Mella Croissant" at a concentration of 413 mg/kg, IgG was 2.80 ± 0.18 mg/ml, and 3.20 ± 0.20 in the control group. When exposed to the drug at a concentration of 413 mg/kg, IgM was 0.10 ± 0.01 mg/ml, and in the control group it was 0.10 ± 0.01 mg/ml.

The experiments show that the feed mixture at a dose of 413 mg/kg did not have a negative effect on the amount of IgG and IgM class immunoglobulins in the peripheral blood serum of experimental animals. The results obtained did not statistically differ from the indicators in the control group. It indicates that there is

no adverse effect (suppression or hyperactivation) on the immunological system of animals.

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